

**Coconut Oil (*Cocos nucifera*) and Beeswax (*Cera alba*)
as a Natural Shoe Polish**

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Cielito Zamora Senior High School

Capstone Project

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Abstract

Title: Coconut Oil (*Cocos nucifera*) and Beeswax (*Cera alba*) as a Natural Shoe Polish

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Synthetic shoe polishes commonly have harmful ingredients that pose risk to health and the environment. Natural ingredients such as beeswax (*Cera alba*), which provide water resistance and a protective layer, and coconut oil (*Cocos nucifera*), known for boosting shine and preventing leather damage, present a promising alternative. However, research on their combined effectiveness as a shoe polish remains limited. Some studies suggest that natural formulations can match or outperform synthetic counterparts in providing a protective layer and enhancing gloss. This study examined the gloss, pH, and melting point of natural and commercial shoe polishes. An experimental design, specifically Completely Randomized Design was employed involving 30 respondents evaluating gloss. The results indicate that the natural shoe polish achieved a higher gloss rating (median = 5.80) compared to the commercial shoe polish (median = 5.00). Statistical analysis using the Mann-Whitney *U* test confirmed this significant difference ($p < .001$). The commercial shoe polish had an average pH of 6.64 and a melting point of 59.80°C, while the natural shoe polish had a pH of 6.76 and a melting point of 57.60°C. No significant differences were observed for pH level ($p = .174$) and melting point

CIELITO ZAMORA SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL

($p = .087$). These findings suggest that coconut oil and beeswax can be an effective, eco-friendly alternative and comparable to their synthetic counterparts. Similar trends in related studies support the viability of natural ingredients in shoe polish formulations.

Keywords: coconut oil, beeswax, shoe polish, completely randomized design, natural shoe polish

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The researchers hereby declare that the work presented herein is original work done and has not been published or submitted elsewhere for the requirement of a degree program. Any literature date or work done by others and cited within this paper has been given due acknowledgement and is listed in the reference section.

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Approval Sheet

This study entitled **Coconut Oil (*Cocos nucifera*) and Beeswax (*Cera alba*) as a Natural Shoe Polish** prepared and submitted by **Jerald G. Bonbon, Aljon Jhon D. Celis, Anthony M. El Mundo, Patricia Mae B. Miranda, Lovely H. Nepomuceno, Ernest James G. Parafina, Cristel Mae V. Rase, Angela Marie A. Robles, and Alessandra Nicole T. Sarap** in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the subject Capstone Project has been examined and recommended for final defense.

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The Researchers

Table of Contents

	Page
Title Page	1
Abstract	2
Copyright Page	4
Approval Sheet	5
Acknowledgement	6
Table of Contents.....	7
List of Tables	9
 Chapter 1: Introduction	
Background, Context, and Significance of the Study	10
Statement of the Problem	12
Hypotheses	13
Review of Related Literature and Studies	13
 Chapter 2: Methods	
Research Design.....	21
Materials and Equipment	22
Biosafety Risk and Assessment	22
Procedures	24
Data Collection	26
Data Analysis	26

Chapter 3: Results and Discussion

The Respondents' Assessment of Gloss of the Commercial Shoe Polish and Coconut Oil (*C. nucifera*) and Beeswax (*C. alba*) Shoe Polish 28

The Chemical and Physical Properties of the Commercial Shoe Polish in Terms of its pH level and Melting Point 31

The Chemical and Physical Properties of the Coconut Oil (*C. nucifera*) and Beeswax (*C. alba*) in Terms of pH Level and Melting Point 32

The Computed Rank Sum, Mann-Whitney *U* test statistic, Probability Values, and Decision on the Significant Difference Between the Respondents' Assessment of Gloss for the Commercial Shoe Polish and the Coconut Oil (*C. nucifera*) and Beeswax (*C. alba*) Shoe Polish 35

The Computed Rank Sum, Mann-Whitney *U* test statistic, Probability Values, and Decision on the Significant Difference Between the pH Level of the Commercial Shoe Polish and the Coconut Oil (*C. nucifera*) and Beeswax (*C. alba*) Natural Shoe Polish 36

The Computed Rank Sum, Mann-Whitney *U* test statistic, Probability Values, and Decision on the Significant Difference Between the Melting Point of the Commercial Shoe Polish and the Coconut Oil (*C. nucifera*) and Beeswax (*C. alba*) Natural Shoe Polish 37

Chapter 4: Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion 39

Recommendations 41

References 43

Appendices 50

List of Tables

Number	Title	Page
1	Respondents' Assessment of Gloss of the Commercial Shoe Polish	29
2	Respondents' Assessment of Gloss of the Coconut Oil (<i>C. nucifera</i>) and Beeswax (<i>C. alba</i>) Shoe Polish	30
3	Chemical and Physical Properties of the Commercial Shoe Polish in Terms of its pH Level and Melting Point	31
4	Chemical and Physical Properties of the Coconut Oil (<i>C. nucifera</i>) and Beeswax (<i>C. alba</i>) Shoe Polish in Terms of its pH level and the Melting Point	33
5	Computed Rank Sum, Mann-Whitney U test statistic, Probability Values, and Decision on the Significant Difference Between the Respondents' Assessment of Gloss for the Commercial Shoe Polish and the Coconut Oil (<i>C. nucifera</i>) and Beeswax (<i>C. alba</i>) Shoe Polish	35
6	Computed Rank Sum, Mann-Whitney U test statistic, Probability Values, and Decision on the Significant Difference Between the pH Level of the Commercial Shoe Polish and the Coconut Oil (<i>C. nucifera</i>) and Beeswax (<i>C. alba</i>) Shoe Polish	36
7	Computed Rank Sum, Mann-Whitney U-test statistic, Probability Values, and Decision on the Significant Difference Between the Melting Point of the Commercial Shoe Polish and the Coconut Oil (<i>C. nucifera</i>) and Beeswax (<i>C. alba</i>) Natural Shoe Polish	37

**Coconut Oil (*Cocos nucifera*) and Beeswax (*Cera alba*)
as a Natural Shoe Polish**

Background, Context, and Significance of the Study

Since the 19th century, the shoe polish sector relied heavily on chemically based formulations that are harmful to both public health and environmental sustainability. This growing concern has led to increasing global awareness and the demand for resulted in an increasing environmental consciousness and the demand for sustainable and eco-friendly alternatives (Luca & Loghin, 2016). As a result, research and innovation have focused on developing natural substitutes for conventional shoe polish ingredients, which are often associated with harmful effects on human health and the environment (Zimmerman & Anastas, 2015).

In response to these concerns, Adiova et al. (2024) explored about the practicability of utilizing radish leaf extract as an alternative shoe polish. This study proved that a natural polish can be produced by utilizing and combining natural ingredients such as radish leaves, coconut oil, soy wax, Gumamela, and calamansi. Unlike other traditional shoe polish, this formulation promotes innovation and advancement without compromising public health and environmental sustainability.

The need for such alternatives is affirmed by Pandey et al. (2023), who affirmed that conventional shoe polishes frequently incorporate hazardous petroleum-based waxes and solvents that pose risks to both human health and environmental integrity. In response to these pressing issues, Akinbomi et al. (2022) advocated for the incorporation of natural, organic ingredients, which have the potential to yield safer formulations that meet consumer performance expectations while minimizing environmental harm.

One such ingredient, coconut oil, aligns with the current trend of using sustainable bioplastic materials, thus providing an alternative method to combat plastic pollution in the

CIELITO ZAMORA SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL

footwear segment (Morganti et al., 2021; Goyal & Jerold, 2021). The combined studies inferred that this waste is rich in oil content and fatty acids, which contribute to the enhanced durability and waterproofing of leather, in addition to providing a glossy finish.

Coconut is an abundant biomass resource in tropical countries such as the Philippines. However, as Mor and Ravindra (2023) pointed out, improper disposal of coconut waste leads to both environmental degradation and lost economic potential. Discarded coconut materials often contribute to pollution, highlighting the need for sustainable solutions that repurpose this waste. One such approach is the development of natural shoe polish which not only provides an affordable and non-toxic alternative but also reduces coconut waste and promoting the use of polish that is safe for public health and ecology.

Research further supports this idea, as organic lipids like beeswax are known for their protective properties. For instance, Nong et al. (2023) demonstrated the skin barrier protective effects of beeswax, highlighting its potential to mitigate adverse health impacts. Beeswax also serves as an effective natural alternative in leather care, forming a moisture-resistant layer that enhances gloss without introducing harmful chemicals.

Given these unique properties, beeswax plays a crucial role in the formulation of shoe polish. It forms a protective coating, providing water resistance and shielding leather from microbial attack (Alabi & Anekwe, 2023; Fratini et al., 2016). This natural wax also enhances the leather's shine, providing both protection and cosmetic benefits (Pinto et al., 2017).

The combination of beeswax and coconut oil creates a sustainable and environmentally friendly alternative to conventional shoe polishes that often contain harmful chemicals. Beeswax offers a natural, non-toxic solution that is safer for both users and the environment (Nong et al., 2023).

This increasing demand for eco-friendly alternatives to conventional shoe care products has spurred research into natural, non-toxic solutions. Beeswax and coconut oil stand out due to

their inherent water resistance and protective qualities, offering a compelling combination for a high-performing, biodegradable shoe polish (Mor & Ravindra., 2023; Vijayan et al., 2023). Despite the promising potential of the natural ingredients, existing research has only partially explored this potential, leaving a significant gap in the market for affordable, effective, and sustainable options. This study directly addresses this gap by developing a natural shoe polish using beeswax and coconut oil. This formulation not only provides superior protection and shine but also meets the growing consumer demand for accessible, affordable, and environmentally responsible footwear care, thereby promoting eco-innovation within the industry.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to evaluate the chemical and physical properties of coconut oil (*Cocos nucifera*) and beeswax (*Cera alba*) as components of a natural shoe polish.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the respondents' assessment of the gloss of commercial shoe polish and the coconut oil (*Cocos nucifera*) and beeswax (*Cera alba*) shoe polish?
2. What is the chemical and physical properties of commercial shoe polish in terms of its:
 - 2.1. pH level; and
 - 2.2. melting point?
3. What is the chemical and physical properties of coconut oil (*Cocos nucifera*) and beeswax (*Cera alba*) shoe polish in terms of:
 - 3.1. pH level; and
 - 3.2. melting point?
4. Is there a significant difference between the respondents' assessment of the gloss of commercial shoe polish and the coconut oil (*Cocos nucifera*) and beeswax (*Cera alba*) shoe polish?

5. Is there a significant difference in the pH level and melting point between the commercial shoe polish and the coconut oil (*Cocos nucifera*) and beeswax (*Cera alba*) natural shoe polish?

Hypotheses

Based on the problem that the study sought to answer, the following hypotheses were tested at a significant level of 0.05:

There is no significant difference between the respondents' assessment of the gloss of commercial shoe polish and the coconut oil (*Cocos nucifera*) and beeswax (*Cera alba*) shoe polish.

There is no significant difference in the pH level and melting point between the commercial shoe polish and the coconut oil (*Cocos nucifera*) and beeswax (*Cera alba*) natural shoe polish.

Review of Related Literature and Studies

This section provided an examination of the current and related studies from reputable sources, such as journals, peer-reviewed articles, books, statements from various government agencies, and statistical data. Moreover, for additional information, a range of relevant literary sources were utilized. It covers a variety of topics, such as a brief overview of beeswax and its properties, as well as the desiccated coconut waste and its possibility of having oil extracted, and the shoe polishes available in the market.

Agricultural Waste

Agricultural waste refers to the byproducts produced from various farming activities. Raut et al. (2023) elaborated that this type of waste includes leftover crop materials, fertilizers, runoff from fields, and other manure and different types of waste from farming operations that polluted

water, air, or soil. Agricultural waste can also come from the processed agricultural products corresponding to fruits, vegetables, dairy, grains and meats.

While the world's population grows wider, the demand for food and meat also increased. This caused the agricultural sector to expand and the waste it produced over time. Obi et al. (2016) explained numerous ways to recycle and generate products out of agricultural wastes, this included the use of coconut wastes.

Coconut waste had been proven to be an efficient raw material for generating byproducts in civil construction, as an adsorbent material, and in the production of ethanol, bio-oil, and organic fertilizers (Vieira et al., 2024). However, Singh et al. (2021) raised concerns on the substantial amount of agro-industrial residue generated in this process, which could pose environmental issues if they are not properly managed. To tackle this issue, Hoang et al. (2024) delve into coconut residues, which they stated to have rich source of phenolic chemicals and oil, which have potential applications in the pharmaceutical industry and are beneficial as anti-inflammatory and antioxidant agents. The said research underscores the significance of repurposing coconut waste, focusing on the utilization and processing of residues to generate sustainable products and byproducts.

Beeswax

Produced by honeybees, the *Cera alba* has been widely utilized throughout history in various fields, including cosmetics, medicine, food processing, and industrial applications. As noted by Shahbaz et al. (2024), beeswax is essential within the bee colony, forming the comb structure where honey is stored, and larvae are nurtured. It is composed of a mix of esters, fatty acids, and hydrocarbons, which give it unique properties like water resistance, flexibility, and a relatively high melting point with it being around 62°C to 64°C (Mousavi et al., 2023; Fair Dinkum Honey, n.d.),

CIELITO ZAMORA SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL

Beeswax is a naturally occurring substance produced by the wax glands of the *Apis mellifera* and *Apis cerana* species. Beeswax is frequently used in cosmetics and body care products because of its strong hydrophobic properties, it is a property of molecules that do not easily become wet in contact with water. Beeswax contains various properties that help prolong the life of leather, make it insoluble in water, resist many acids, and add gloss. Given that a growing number of individuals are realizing the benefits of using beeswax to treat a variety of illnesses, beeswax has regained popularity in the medical community (Kurek-Górecka et al., 2020).

Studies have examined the compatibility of beeswax to natural oils in producing a natural shoe polish. This builds on research by Zhang et al. (2018), who demonstrated that beeswax effectively combines with natural substances to improve properties like moisture resistance and thermal stability - characteristics essential for shoe polish formulation

According to research conducted by Nong et al. (2023), varied uses of beeswax in the modern day. In skincare, beeswax can be low-cost; it has natural ingredients that are more accessible for cosmetic products. Beeswax has proven to be beneficial for protecting the skin barrier, scientific literature reviewed that beeswax can be used as a natural way to help maintain skin hydration, ease inflammatory symptoms associated with skin like atopic dermatitis or contact irritants dermatitis, and alleviate side effects of burns. Beeswax remains widely used in cosmetics, adding soothing qualities, and enhancing brilliance.

As outlined in the study of Alabi (2023), beeswax is naturally effective and possesses the appropriate properties that act as a protective agent, hence enhancing the shine and endurance of the polish. The two materials could provide an avenue for the development of a product that would be effective and friendly to the environment. Wax of the bee is one natural product. It is produced by the wax glands of the species *Apis mellifera* and *Apis cerana*. The material used during the process of comb building to be used for storage of their honey is wax obtained from

bees. Beeswax contained high contents of long-chain alcohols and fatty acids. Beeswax was used as early as the 14th century in cosmetics and as a medication (Shahbaz et al., 2024).

The study by Szulc et al. (2020) assessed the antimicrobial activity of beeswax fabrics against bacteria and fungi. Given the growing concerns about microorganisms' resistance to chemical compounds and the toxic effects of biocides on the environment, new environmental materials and substances are being sought for endowing textiles with antimicrobial properties. The results show that the process of finishing fabrics through the application of beeswax may endow the anti-mold activity that can find practical application.

Additionally, its natural antibacterial properties protect leather from mold and mildew, contributing to the product's longevity. Given the rising environmental and health concerns linked to conventional shoe polishes, such as those containing nitrobenzene.

Moreover, the incorporation of natural ingredients such as beeswax in polishes is acknowledged for delivering a durable and superior finish, improving the appearance and longevity of leather (Better Homes & Gardens, 2023).

Zhang et al. (2018) conducted a study that tested the effects of beeswax and carnauba wax as an addition to the properties of gelatin films. The study showed that the addition of beeswax and carnauba wax has improved gelatin films' capacity to serve as the thermal stability of the gelatin-wax films and a barrier to light and moisture, which are the key factors that lead to oxidation, degradation, and deterioration. The results have shown that beeswax was better than carnauba wax in terms of improving various properties of gelatin films.

Moreover, the study by Bayir et al. in 2019 tested the therapeutic effects of adding beeswax, olive oil, and butter, commonly referred to as BOB to ointment for second-degree burn wounds. These organic materials are proven to nourish the skin as they play a crucial role in regeneration, thus improving the healing process involving visible regeneration.

Many investigations have demonstrated the beneficial effects of adding beeswax to different cosmetic products, and the application of these products in healing highlights their therapeutic efficacy. The benefit of medicines and cosmetics based on bee products is their effectiveness with minimal side effects. One such study is done by Kurek-Górecka et al. (2020) which reveals that beeswax is an emulsifier of cosmetic forms.

Coconut Oil

Eyres et al. (2016) defined coconut oil as a byproduct of coconut milk extraction. According to Kappally et al. (2015), it contains saturated fatty acids and medium-chain fatty acids, which confirms that it is an oil. Numerous research studies have concluded that the utilization of coconut oil benefits skin care and other applications (Wallace, 2018).

According to Narayanankutty et al. (2018) edible oils including coconut oil, have been a part of the diet of a humans since ancient civilizations. With the composition of fatty acids, these oils are rich in polyunsaturated, monounsaturated, and saturated fatty acids. Coconut oil has a melting point of 24°C to 25°C (Norton, 2018)

The utilization of coconut oil has gained its wave of popularity due to its high levels of saturations and excellent stability, with 90% of its composition consistently having saturated fatty acid, this is a higher proportion ratio, unlike other vegetable oils in the market.

In line with this, the research by Asuncion and Villarico (2015) investigated the efficacy of a natural shoe polish composed of calamansi extract and coconut oil. Calamansi, a citrus fruit recognized for its acidic properties, helps eliminate dirt and stains, while coconut oil added shine and is hypoallergenic, presenting a safer option compared to conventional polishes that frequently contain harmful chemicals. The study intends to show that this environmentally friendly blend not only cleans and protects footwear but is also economical and easily available, benefiting both consumers and the environment.

Shoe Polish

Shoe polish is used to clean, shine, and protect leather footwear; it dates to the 18th century when natural oils and waxes were employed to condition leather. Modern shoe polish formulations consist of a blend of waxes, solvents, and dyes, providing a glossy and durable finish (Charles, 2019). According to Jones et al. (2020), common waxes such as carnauba and beeswax are integral to shoe polish because they form a water-resistant barrier that helps prolong the life of leather footwear.

As a wax-based product, shoe polish is used primarily for the maintenance and enhancement of leather footwear. It serves multiple functions, such as offering gloss, fading resistance, and dust protection. Various formulations exist, often incorporating natural and synthetic ingredients to achieve desired properties (Derbe et al., 2021; Cacatian & Ouano, 2020).

However, Adiova's work (2024) suggests that unsafe chemicals are still present in many shoe polishes. The research shows that many shoe polish formulations help to preserve harmful substances such as nitrobenzene, toluene, formaldehyde, glycol ethers, and heavy metals – lead. Most of these chemicals can be linked to health problems or toxicity that can range from the most immediate, such as skin and respiratory disorders, to long-latency effects like neurological damage, reproductive dysfunction, or even cancer. The study also enumerates the large-scale environmental risks, including the pollution of water and air, soil pollution, and the risks of bioaccumulation in nature.

One of the scholarly works presented by Pandey (2023), has revealed that conventional shoe polishes have traditionally used waxes and solvents of petroleum-based materials, which result in harm to human health as well as the environment. Moreover, synthetic shoe polishes often contain silicones that form a protective layer over the leather, potentially sealing it and limiting its natural breathability (The ShoeCare-Shop, n.d.). In this regard, naturally available ingredients could be mixed to create a formulation that would meet consumer expectations in

terms of performance but also assist in minimizing the potentially harmful environmental impacts of traditional shoe polishes with unsafe chemicals (Akinbomi et al., 2022).

According to Dongqiong (2017), demonstrating the preparation in making shoe polish entails creating a black liquid, mixing paraffin, beeswax, stearic acid, silicone oil, and treated fibers. The steps in the preparation process for shoe polish are as follows: (1) create a black liquid by mixing black dye; (2) combine solid paraffin and beeswax, add to the black liquid, stir, and heat to fuse; this creates a colloidal liquid, 3) combining silicone oil and stearic acid with the colloidal liquid to create a thick mixed liquid; (4) ultrasonically treating natural fibers to produce treated fibers, then adding the treated fibers to the combined liquid and thoroughly stirring. The methodically produced shoe polish has an excellent cleaning effect on leather shoes.

In the study conducted by Pandey et al. (2023), they developed a shoe polish based on Karanj oil, the impact of shellac, and gum Arabic in its formulation. It was stated that to overcome the problem of color, sixteen various combinations of shellac and gum Arabic for improvement of black and brown polish. Tests were conducted on the produced shoe polish to determine its texture, application, spreadability, and ease of removal. A gloss meter was used to record the color of the polish. The created sample was found very near to standard brand shoe polish based on gloss value and sensory evaluation, with the exception that it initially gave off an oily appearance.

Derbe et al. (2020) conducted a study where shoe polish was prepared from cactus powder, charcoal powder, wax, and oil in the presence of denatured alcohol and benzene at an optimized procedure. It showed that the prepared shoe polish has shown comparable results with purchased shoe polish such as Kiwi. The prepared shoe polish exhibited a very good gloss, dust adsorption resistance, fading resistance, and rub resistance. The perceived efficacy, sustainability, and safety of ingredients frequently influence the preference for natural components (McKinsey & Company, 2021; Eisen et al., 2024). Thus, the prepared shoe polish

CIELITO ZAMORA SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL

was fulfilled with quality and replaceable with the commercially available shoe polish on the market.

Akinbomi et al. (2022) stated that having appropriate shoe polish viscosity and melting point is important for customer satisfaction as too thick or too thin shoe polish may not result in desired customer satisfaction. The difference in viscosities of the shoe polish samples was observed when the process temperature was below 60°C. Floros et al. (2017) assert that stability in melting point is crucial for preserving the polish's consistency, viscosity, and efficacy over time.

Chapter 2

Methods

Research Design

In this particular study, the researchers employed the use of descriptive research and experimental research. The researchers utilized descriptive research to determine consumer assessment of the gloss of the product. According to Sekar and Bhuvanewari (2024), descriptive research is a method used to systematically describe the characteristics of a population or phenomenon, often through surveys and observations. This approach allowed the researchers to gather numerical data that provided insights into consumer perceptions of the product's gloss intensity.

The comparison in gloss was performed using various leather samples, treated with commercial and natural shoe polish throughout five trials; hence, the experimental design for this is a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with Independent Groups. A Completely Randomized Design (CRD) guarantees that each experimental unit is randomly allocated to treatments, thereby reducing bias and enhancing the precision of the results (Montgomery, 2020). Moreover, this research employed an experimental design to investigate the pH level and melting point of shoe polish. Webber and Prouse (2024) discussed how this design explores the relationships between independent and dependent variables by means of controlled manipulation. Consequently, this research examined the differences between commercial and natural shoe polish by assessing its gloss, pH level, and melting point, aiming to determine how effectively the natural formulation performs in comparison to a commercial alternative.

Materials and Equipment

This study required the use of the following materials: beeswax, coconut oil that came from the coconut waste, beaker, stirring rod, tripod, denatured alcohol, alcohol lamp, weighing scale, wire gauze, test tube, test tube holder, thermometer, pH meter, and plastic container.

Biosafety and Risk Assessment

While the project involved the use of natural materials for creating a shoe polish from Coconut Oil (*Cocos nucifera*) and Beeswax (*Cera alba*), it is crucial to assess potential biosafety hazards related to the handling and processing of these materials. The following potential risks for this study were identified

Allergenic Sensitivity

Coconut oil (*C nucifera*) and beeswax (*C. alba*) may provoke allergic responses in people with sensitivity. There is potential for dermatological and respiratory complications, especially in individuals who have known allergies to plant-based oils or bee-derived products.

Inhalation of Fume

Inhaling fumes from heated shoe polish products may pose respiratory hazards. Some ingredients in commercial polishes can release volatile organic compound or other harmful fumes when exposed to heat, which could irritate the respiratory tract and eyes

Thermal Processing Hazard

Heating the commercial shoe polish and the natural shoe polish can release volatile organic compounds during the production process. However, exposure to heated food and

chemicals, particulates, and vapors can also irritate respiratory stressors during the manual mixing and heating phase for prolonged exposure.

Microbial Contamination

Organic materials, coconut oil and beeswax can harbor microbial activity if they are not properly handled or stored. These risks can lead to the growth of fungi and bacteria that affect product quality and contain pathogenic microorganisms.

Risks of Cross Contamination

Environmental contaminants could be introduced during important equipment processes such as material preparations, mixing, and packaging phases of production. Improper handling methods can result in cross-contamination with foreign biological or chemical agents.

Potential Skin Exposure Complications

Direct contact with raw materials may cause skin irritation, contact dermatitis, or allergic responses, especially for individuals with heightened sensitivity to natural oil-based substances.

Likewise, establishing protective measures is crucial for ensuring biosafety and effectively managing risks, particularly for this study. This involves addressing potential hazards, assessing exposure risks, and implementing safety protocols related to materials, experiments, and waste disposal.

While working with the commercial and natural shoe polish, it is essential to wear personal protective equipment (PPE), including gloves, to prevent any allergic reactions. For individuals with allergies, skin patch tests could be necessary, in addition to using protective barriers such as masks. It is essential to store materials in clean, dry containers to prevent contamination and to ensure they are kept away from moisture. Conducting experiments that involve heating should

be done in areas with good ventilation to minimize exposure to fumes. Equipment that monitors temperature is essential for managing thermal levels and ensuring the prevention of hazardous vapors. Adhering to rigorous sanitation practices, such as ensuring tools are cleaned and workspaces are kept tidy, is essential for preventing cross-contamination. To protect the environment, organic and chemical waste must be separated and stored in designated containers.

Procedures

The following steps are carried out to make the shoe polish made from coconut (*Cocos nucifera*) oil and beeswax (*Cera alba*).

1. **Collection of Materials.** The coconut waste was sourced from a local market at no cost, and the beeswax was procured through an online shopping platform.
2. **Extraction of Oil from Coconut Waste.** The extraction process involved hot water treatment, wherein hot water was poured over the coconut waste to release any remaining milk. The extracted milk was then subjected to boiling to separate and obtain the oil.
3. **Melting of Beeswax.** A measured quantity of beeswax was melted in a beaker with continuous stirring under controlled heating conditions, to ensure uniform melting and prevent clumping.
4. **Mixing Process.** A specified ratio of coconut oil measured in milliliters (mL) was added to a predetermined quantity of melted beeswax, measured in grams (g). During the process, the heating element was turned off and the mixture was continuously stirred until it reached room temperature to ensure uniform consistency.
5. **Product Testing and Data Gathering.** The commercial and the natural shoe polish were subjected to respondents' assessment to evaluate its gloss. Additionally, its physical properties were analyzed by measuring its pH level and melting point.

5.1 Glossiness. Laid down by Chadwick and Kentridge (2015), gloss is an optical property that indicates how well light reflects off a surface. Measuring gloss remains a challenging process, as such, due to its complexities, the researchers employed the use of questionnaires and respondents sampled by convenience in determining the glossiness of the products given by the varied formulations.

5.2 pH level. According to Kumar and Lokhande (2024), the potential of hydrogen or pH level is a measurement of acidity or the basicity of a solution, expressed logarithmically ranging from 0 to 14. Adiova et al. (2024) and Baglioni et al. (2016) stated that a pH level of 6-7 is the most preferred as it suggests suitability for its purpose. The researchers utilized EZDO PH-5011 Meter to test the pH level of the shoe polish.

5.3 Melting Point. It is a thermophysical property that shows the temperature when a solid becomes a liquid, it plays a significant role in the shoe polish as it will ensure the product stability and effective usage (Adiova et al., 2024; Delele et al., 2021). The melting point was determined by heating 200 mL of water in a beaker, starting at 35°C, and gradually increasing the temperature until fully melted. A test tube containing 10 mL of the shoe polish formulation was submerged in the beaker during the process.

6. *Interpreting and Analyzing the Results of the Testing.* The researchers systematically organized, processed, and analyzed the collected data to derive meaningful interpretations. Descriptive and statistical analyses were conducted to evaluate the results of the consumer assessment on gloss, as well as the measured chemical and physical properties, including pH level and melting point respectively. The findings were then assessed to determine significant differences and overall effectiveness of the natural shoe polish formulation.

Data Collection

This research sought to assess how well coconut oil (*Cocos nucifera*) and beeswax (*Cera alba*) work together as a natural shoe polish. Coconut waste was gathered from a nearby market in Caloocan City, and beeswax was obtained through an online platform. To evaluate the effectiveness of the commercial and natural shoe polishes' gloss, the convenience sampling method was used. This involved the selection of 30 Grade 11 STEM students from 11-Leibniz as respondents were selected based on their accessibility and availability. Convenience sampling is a non-probability sampling technique that entails selecting participants based on their accessibility and readiness to engage. This approach prioritizes accessibility over random selection, rendering it a pragmatic option for studies constrained by time or resources. (Stratton, 2021). The gloss was evaluated through questionnaires filled out by respondents. The formulated shoe polish is then subjected to testing with five separate trials to assess its pH level and melting point. The school laboratory of Cielito Zamora Senior High School served as the venue for the product testing conducted.

Data Analysis

In order to ensure proper interpretation and significant insights, the researchers used statistical techniques to methodically assess the gathered data. Likewise, to have a better understanding of the data, the researchers utilized the weighted mean and Mann-Whitney U Test to effectively organize, summarize, and interpret the collected data in tabular form.

According to Lee et al. (2016), a weighted mean is a statistical tool that is used to check for the relative importance of different values in data. Unlike the simple arithmetic mean, the weighted mean assigns different weights for each data point, allowing for a more advanced, complex grouping of information.

The formula to calculate the weighted mean is as follows:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum fx}{n}$$

Where:

\bar{x} = weighted mean

f = frequency in each class

x = midpoint of each class

n = total frequency

Moreover, a Mann-Whitney U Test was conducted to determine whether there is a significant difference in the respondents' assessments of commercial shoe polish and natural shoe polish made from coconut oil (*Cocos nucifera*) and beeswax (*Cera alba*).

The Mann-Whitney U Test is a non-parametric statistical test used when the data does not meet the assumptions of normality, making it a suitable choice for this study as it effectively compares the distributions of continuous variables, such as pH levels and melting points, without requiring normality assumptions. Additionally, it is appropriate for this study due to the relatively small sample size utilized in this study (MacFarland & Yates, 2016).

The formula for the Mann-Whitney U Test is as follows:

$$U = n_1n_2 + \frac{n_1(n_1 + 1)}{2} - R_1$$

$$U = n_1n_2 + \frac{n_2(n_2 + 1)}{2} - R_2$$

$$U = \min(U_1, U_2)$$

Where:

U = Mann-Whitney U-statistic

n_1 = sample size of the first group

n_2 = sample size of the second group

R_1 = sum of the ranks for the first group

R_2 = sum of the ranks for the second group

Chapter 3

Results and Discussion

This chapter discusses quantitative measurements from various data collection methods and their analyses. The results of this chapter focus on evaluating the chemical and physical characteristics of shoe polish made from coconut oil (*Cocos nucifera*) and beeswax (*Cera alba*), in comparison to commercial shoe polish. The chapter especially examines the respondents' assessments of gloss, and the comparison of the pH level and melting point between the commercial and natural shoe polishes. Furthermore, statistical evaluation are conducted to find notable differences between the natural and commercial shoe polish on their aspects.

1. What is the respondents' assessment of the gloss of commercial shoe polish and the coconut oil (*Cocos nucifera*) and beeswax (*Cera alba*) natural shoe polish?

This section explores the respondents' assessment of the gloss quality of both the commercial shoe polish and the natural shoe polish composed of coconut oil (*Cocos nucifera*) and beeswax (*Cera alba*). The collected data indicates the participants' assessments, offering insights into the comparison between the natural formulation and the commercial one regarding its shine on leather.

Table 1

Respondents' Assessment of Gloss of the Commercial Shoe Polish

Glossiness	Weighted Mean	Adjectival Rating
1. The shoe polish delivers a gloss upon application.	5.07	Agree
2. The polish provides a good gloss finish on the leather.	4.80	Agree
3. The shoe polish enhances the leather's natural gloss effectively.	4.70	Agree
4. The gloss achieved from the shoe polish remains consistent over time.	5.10	Agree
5. The polish does not leave streaks or uneven patches on the leather surface.	4.77	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	4.89	Agree

<i>Legend:</i>	5.16 – 6.00	Strongly Agree	2.67 – 3.49	Slightly Disagree
	4.33 – 5.15	Agree	1.84 – 2.66	Disagree
	3.50 – 4.32	Slightly Agree	1.00 – 1.83	Strongly Disagree

Table 1 presents respondents' evaluation of the gloss of commercial shoe polish. The highest weighted mean of 5.10 suggests that the gloss produced by this polish is consistently maintained over time, highlighting a generally positive view of its effectiveness. The lowest weighted mean of 4.70, associated with improving the leather's natural gloss, remains in the agree category. This indicates that respondents recognize its effectiveness, yet they do not regard it as favorably as the natural alternative. The overall weighted mean of 4.89, classified as agree, reflects a general satisfaction.

The lower ratings of the commercial polish can be linked to various factors, including the presence of synthetic ingredients. Many consumers tend to view these ingredients as less appealing compared to natural alternatives. Synthetic shoe polishes frequently include silicones that create a protective barrier over the leather, which may completely seal it and restrict its natural breathability (The ShoeCare-Shop, n.d.). This trait may encourage consumers to prefer natural polishes, which help the leather preserve its breathability and extend its lifespan. The results indicate that consumers are likely to value not only the effectiveness of a product but also its

ingredients, highlighting the increasing trend of environmentally aware purchasing choices in the shoe care industry (Eisen et al., 2024).

Table 2

Respondents' Assessment of Gloss of the Coconut Oil (C. nucifera) and Beeswax (C. alba) Shoe Polish

Glossiness	Weighted Mean	Adjectival Rating
1. The shoe polish delivers a gloss upon application.	5.90	Strongly Agree
2. The polish provides a good gloss finish on the leather.	5.77	Strongly Agree
3. The natural shoe polish enhances the leather's natural gloss effectively.	5.63	Strongly Agree
4. The gloss achieved from the natural shoe polish remains consistent over time.	5.83	Strongly Agree
5. The polish does not leave streaks or uneven patches on the leather surface.	5.70	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	5.77	Strongly Agree

Legend:

5.16 – 6.00	Strongly Agree	2.67 – 3.49	Slightly Disagree
4.33 – 5.15	Agree	1.84 – 2.66	Disagree
3.50 – 4.32	Slightly Agree	1.00 – 1.83	Strongly Disagree

The respondents' evaluation of the natural shoe polish made from coconut oil and beeswax in terms of glossiness is shown in Table 2. The highest weighted mean of 5.90 suggests that respondents are in strong agreement regarding the polish's effectiveness in providing a gloss upon application, thereby improving the appearance of shoes. The lowest weighted mean of 5.63, associated with the improvement of the leather's natural gloss, falls within the strongly agree category, reflecting a favorable view of every aspect of glossiness. The overall weighted mean of 5.77 suggests that respondents generally feel positively about the polish's ability to provide a glossy finish to leather.

The results align with consumer inclinations towards natural and eco-friendly products. The use of natural ingredients like beeswax in shoe polish is recognized for providing a lasting and high-quality finish, enhancing both the look and durability of leather (Better Homes &

Gardens, 2023). Perceptions of the ingredients' efficacy, sustainability, and safety often impact the preference for natural ingredients (McKinsey & Company, 2021). The consensus among various aspects suggests that using coconut oil and beeswax as key ingredients effectively meets consumer expectations, highlighting the potential of natural shoe polish to compete with synthetic alternatives.

2. What is the chemical and physical properties of the commercial shoe polish in terms of its:

2.1. pH level; and

2.2. melting point?

This section explores the chemical and physical properties of the commercial shoe polish, focusing on its pH level and melting point respectively. The pH level offers a glimpse into how acidic or alkaline the product is, which can influence how it interacts with various surfaces. Meanwhile, the melting point reveals important information about its thermal behavior and how it can be used in different environmental conditions. This section's findings provide a valuable reference point for comparing with the natural shoe polish formulation.

Table 3

Chemical and Physical Properties of the Commercial Shoe Polish in Terms of its pH Level and Melting Point

Trials	Commercial Shoe Polish	
	pH level	Melting Point (°C)
I	6.70	58.50
II	6.66	61.00
III	6.65	60.50
IV	6.75	60.00
V	6.46	59.00
Mean	6.64	59.80

Table 3 presents the pH levels and melting points of a commercial shoe polish across five trials. The pH values were recorded across five trials. Trial IV exhibited the highest pH level at 6.75, indicating the most neutral formulation, while Trial V had the lowest at 6.46, suggesting a slightly more acidic composition. The mean pH level was 6.64, indicating that the shoe polish formulation is slightly acidic to neutral. A neutral pH is beneficial in ensuring the polish does not cause skin irritation while maintaining its effectiveness in protecting and enhancing shoe surfaces. The recorded pH values suggests that the polish is designed to be gentle on leather, minimizing the risk of material degradation. The study of Adiova et al. (2024) underscored that maintaining a near-neutral pH in leather care products is crucial, as it helps preserve the leather's integrity and prevents issues such as brittleness or discoloration.

The melting points were recorded across five trials. Trial II exhibited the highest melting point at 61.00°C, indicating a more heat-resistant formulation, while Trial I had the lowest at 58.50°C, suggesting a softer consistency. The mean melting point was 59.80°C. A higher melting point indicates that the polish remains stable under moderate temperatures, ensuring it does not melt or become too soft during storage or use. According to the study of Floros et al. (2017), this stability is essential for maintaining the polish's consistency and effectiveness over time. The consistent melting point values across trials suggest a well-formulated product, balancing various waxes and oils to achieve the desired hardness and application properties

3. What is the chemical and physical properties of coconut oil (*Cocos nucifera*) and beeswax (*Cera alba*) shoe polish in terms of:

3.1. pH level; and

3.2. melting point?

This section delves into the chemical and physical characteristics of the natural shoe polish crafted from coconut oil (*Cocos nucifera*) and beeswax (*Cera alba*), highlighting its pH level and melting point. The pH level provides insight into the acidity or alkalinity of the product,

affecting its interaction with different surfaces. At the same time, the melting point provides valuable insights into its thermal behavior and potential applications across various environmental conditions.

Table 4

Chemical and Physical Properties of the Coconut Oil (C. nucifera) and Beeswax (C. alba) Shoe Polish in terms of its pH level and the Melting Point

Trials	Natural Shoe Polish	
	pH level	Melting Point (°C)
I	6.56	58.00
II	6.86	57.00
III	6.70	54.00
IV	6.80	59.50
V	6.89	59.50
Mean	6.76	57.60

Table 4 provides an overview of the pH levels and melting points for a natural shoe polish made from ingredients like beeswax and coconut oil. The pH values were recorded across five trials. Trial 5 exhibited the highest pH level at 6.89, making it the closest to a neutral (pH=7), result, and Trial 3 recorded the lowest is 6.56. The mean pH was 6.76. This suggests a slightly elevated, but still close to neutral pH when compared to the commercial polish. Furthermore, Adiova et al. (2024) explained that maintaining a near-neutral pH helps reduce the chances of chemical interactions that might harm leather fibers as time goes on, thereby safeguarding the material's integrity and look.

Moreover, the natural shoe polish exhibited a balanced melting point influenced by the thermal properties of beeswax and coconut oil. The melting point were recorded across the five trials, wherein both Trial IV and V exhibiting the highest melting point at 59.50°C and Trial III having the lowest at 54.00°C. This aligns with the known melting points of the two components used, beeswax, which melts between 62°C and 64°C, provides heat resistance, and coconut oil,

with a melting point of around 24°C to 25°C, which lowers the overall melting point, resulting in a softer texture that enhances ease of application (Fair Dinkum Honey, n.d.; Norton, 2018). The stability of this formulation is crucial, as it prevents excessive hardening or softening under varying environmental conditions, ensuring consistent performance (Derbe et al., 2021). A well-balanced melting point helps maintain the polish's integrity, preventing it from becoming overly brittle in colder conditions or too fluid in warmer ones. This balance ensures a reliable application and effective protection for the leather.

4. Is there a significant difference between the respondents' assessment of gloss of the commercial shoe polish and the coconut oil (*Cocos nucifera*) and beeswax (*Cera alba*) shoe polish?

This section examines whether there is a significant difference between the respondents' assessment of gloss for the commercial shoe polish and the natural shoe polish formulated with coconut oil (*Cocos nucifera*) and beeswax (*Cera alba*). Statistical analyses were conducted to compare the perceived shine of both formulations, determining whether the natural alternative provides a comparable gloss effect. The results offer insights into consumer preference and the potential viability of the natural shoe polish as an alternative to commercial products.

Table 5

Computed Rank Sum, Mann-Whitney U test statistic, Probability Values, and Decision on the Significant Difference Between the Respondents' Assessment of Gloss for the Commercial Shoe Polish and the Coconut Oil (C. nucifera) and Beeswax (C. alba) Shoe Polish

Shoe polishes	Count	Median	RS	U	SD	p	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
Commercial Shoe Polish	30	5.00	618.50	746.00	67.638	0.000	Reject H ₀	Significant
Natural Shoe Polish	30	5.80	1211.50	153.50				

Note: RS – Rank Sum, U – Mann-Whitney U test statistic, SD – Standard Deviation, p – Probability Value, H₀ – Null Hypothesis

Table 5 presents a comparative analysis of respondents' gloss assessment between natural and commercial shoe polishes, demonstrating a significant difference in their performance. The natural shoe polish achieved a median glossiness rating of 5.80, while the commercial shoe polish received a median rating of 5.00. The computed Mann-Whitney *U* value is 153.50, with a $p < .001$, which is below the significance threshold ($\alpha = .05$). Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating that the natural shoe polish was perceived as glossier than the commercial one.

The natural polish exhibits a higher median gloss value compared to the commercial shoe polish, as evidenced by the statistical analysis. This suggests that the natural formulation may enhance the glossiness of leather footwear, potentially offering an advantage over synthetic alternatives in the market (Cacatian & Ouano, 2020). Moreover, research indicates that natural waxes yield a durable and visually appealing finish on leather surfaces (Cacatian & Ouano, 2020). Conversely, commercial polishes typically include synthetic ingredients that may not achieve equivalent gloss or consistency, which could result in inconsistent user experiences (Akinbomi et al., 2022).

5. Is there a significant difference in the pH level and melting point between the commercial shoe polish and the coconut oil (*Cocos nucifera*) and beeswax (*Cera alba*) shoe polish?

This section analyzes whether there is a significant difference in the pH level and melting point between commercial shoe polish and natural shoe polish formulated with coconut oil (*C. nucifera*) and beeswax (*C. alba*). The pH level comparison provides insights into the acidity or alkalinity of each formulation, which may influence their interaction with shoe materials. Meanwhile, the melting point analysis determines the thermal behavior of both products, affecting their application and stability under different temperature conditions. Mann-Whitney *U*-test was used as the statistical tool for determining if there were any significant differences between the two shoe polish formulations in the assessed variables.

Table 6

Computed Rank Sum, Mann-Whitney U test statistic, Probability Values, and Decision on the Significant Difference Between the pH Level of the Commercial Shoe Polish and the Coconut Oil (C. nucifera) and Beeswax (C. alba) Shoe Polish

Shoe polishes	Count	Median	RS	U	SD	p	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
Commercial Shoe Polish	5	6.65	20.50	19.50	4.787	0.174	Fail to Reject H ₀	Not Significant
Natural Shoe Polish	5	6.80	34.50	5.50				

Note: RS – Rank Sum, U – Mann-Whitney U test statistic, SD – Standard Deviation, p –Probability Value, H₀ – Null Hypothesis

Table 6 presents data from five trials of pH testing conducted to compare the pH levels of commercial shoe polish and a natural shoe polish formulated with coconut oil (*C. nucifera*) and beeswax (*C. alba*). A Mann-Whitney *U*-test was utilized to determine whether there was a significant difference between the pH levels of the two shoe polishes.

The results indicate that the median pH level of the natural shoe polish is 6.80, while the commercial shoe polish has a median pH level of 6.65. The Mann-Whitney *U* test yielded a computed *U* value of 5.50, with a *p*-value of .174, which exceeds the significance level ($\alpha = .05$). Since the *p*-value is greater than .05, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected, suggesting that there is no statistically significant difference between the pH levels of the two shoe polishes.

The similarity in pH levels between the natural and commercial shoe polishes indicates that the natural formulation is comparable to its commercial counterpart in terms of acidity or alkalinity. This is likewise stated in the study of Adiova et al. (2024) and Cacatian (2016). The studies also stated that maintaining a pH level close to neutral is essential, as it ensures compatibility with leather materials, which typically have a slightly acidic pH.

Table 7

Computed Rank Sum, Mann-Whitney U-test statistic, Probability Values, and Decision on the Significant Difference Between the Melting Point of the Commercial Shoe Polish and the Coconut Oil (C. nucifera) and Beeswax (C. alba) Natural Shoe Polish

Shoe polishes	Count	Median	RS	U	SD	p	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
Commercial Shoe Polish	5	60.00	36.00	21.00			Fail to	Not
Natural Shoe Polish	5	58.00	19.00	4.00	4.787	0.087	Reject H ₀	Significant

Note: RS – Rank Sum, U – Mann-Whitney U value, SD – Standard Deviation, p – Probability Value, H₀ – Null Hypothesis

Table 7 shares insights from five trials focused on melting point testing, aimed at comparing the melting points of commercial shoe polish with a natural alternative made from coconut oil (*C. nucifera*) and beeswax (*C. alba*). A Mann-Whitney U test was conducted to determine whether there was a significant difference in the melting points of the two shoe polishes.

The results indicate that the median melting point of natural shoe polish is 58°C, while commercial shoe polish has a median melting point of 60°C. The Mann-Whitney U test yielded a computed *U* value of 4.00, with a p-value of .087, which exceeds the significance level ($\alpha = .05$). Since the p-value is greater than α , the null hypothesis cannot be rejected, indicating no statistically significant difference in the melting points of the two shoe polish samples.

The melting points of both natural and commercial shoe polishes show a notable similarity, suggesting that the natural shoe polish holds its own against the commercial version when it comes to thermal stability. It was echoed by Adiova et al. (2024) that keeping a melting point similar to that of commercial products helps natural shoe polish stay reliable during regular storage and use.

Chapter 4

Conclusion and Recommendations

This chapter offers an in-depth analysis of the results outlined in the preceding chapter and examines their wider implications thoroughly. It examines the data analysis process, emphasizing the principal findings and their relevance to the study's objectives. Through careful analysis of the results, significant conclusions are derived that enhance understanding of the study. Furthermore, relevant suggestions and recommendations are presented based on the findings to guide future research and applications in this area.

Conclusion

Based on the analyzed results and findings, the researchers have drawn the following conclusions on the formulation of a natural shoe polish using coconut oil (*Cocos nucifera*) and beeswax (*Cera alba*).

In response to the growing demand for eco-friendly and sustainable alternatives, this study explored the feasibility of these natural ingredients in producing an effective shoe polish. The evaluation focused on key product aspects, particularly glossiness, pH level, melting point, and its overall effectiveness to determine its potential as an effective alternative to commercialized shoe polish.

As for glossiness, the natural shoe polish composed of coconut oil (*C. nucifera*) and beeswax (*C. alba*) obtained a higher weighted mean compared to the commercial shoe polish. This suggests that the natural formulation provides a noticeable shine to leather surfaces, making it a suitable option for individuals seeking a polished appearance for their footwear. The higher gloss rating of the natural shoe polish may be attributed to the properties of beeswax (*C. alba*), which creates a protective, moisture-resistant layer that enhances the reflective quality of the

leather. Additionally, the findings correspond with consumer preferences for environmentally sustainable products that incorporate natural ingredients as commercial polishes often contain synthetic ingredients that may affect gloss and consistency, leading to varying user experiences.

For the pH level of the commercial shoe polish and the natural shoe polish, it was recorded to fall within the ideal pH range for leather care, ensuring compatibility with the material while preventing potential degradation. Though the slightly higher pH level of the natural shoe polish may be attributed to the presence of coconut oil (*C. nucifera*), which contains natural fatty acids that influence the formulation's acidity. These findings highlight the ability of coconut oil (*C. nucifera*) and beeswax (*C. alba*) to create an effective, leather-friendly shoe polish without compromising product quality.

For the melting point, the commercial and natural shoe polish formulated with coconut oil (*C. nucifera*) and beeswax (*C. alba*) exhibited distinct melting points, influencing their stability and usability. The natural polish, formulated with beeswax and coconut oil, demonstrated a well-balanced melting point, making it softer and easier to apply while maintaining stability under varying conditions. Similarly, the commercial polish displayed a consistent melting point, indicating a well-formulated blend of waxes and oils that enhances heat resistance and prevents excessive softening or hardening.

Moreover, the commercial shoe polish and the natural shoe polish formulated with coconut oil (*C. nucifera*) and beeswax (*C. alba*) have shown significant differences in terms of gloss perception. The statistical analysis, as determined by the Mann-Whitney U test, revealed that the natural shoe polish attained a higher median glossiness rating compared to its commercial counterpart. This finding suggests that the natural formulation provides more reflectivity, indicating its potential as an effective and preferable alternative to conventional synthetic shoe polishes.

However, the results indicated no significant difference between the pH levels and melting points of the natural and commercial shoe polishes. The natural shoe polish, formulated with

coconut oil and beeswax, exhibited a melting point comparable to that of commercial polish, suggesting similar thermal stability. This stability helps prevent excessive softening or hardening under varying temperatures, ensuring consistent usability. Additionally, the comparable pH levels of both formulations indicate that the natural shoe polish maintains a balance suitable for leather materials.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the researchers propose the following recommendations for the future development and application of a natural shoe polish using coconut oil (*Cocos nucifera*) and beeswax (*Cera alba*).

For glossiness, the natural shoe polish exhibited higher gloss ratings as assessed by respondents compared to commercial shoe polish, indicating its effectiveness in enhancing the shine of leather without the use of synthetic ingredients. To further improve gloss retention, adjustments in the ratio of coconut oil and beeswax can be explored. Future studies may also assess the long-term durability of the polish under varying environmental conditions.

Consequently, it is noted in the results that the commercial shoe polish demonstrated a stable pH level and a slightly higher melting point, ensuring consistency in different temperatures. Since maintaining these properties is crucial for leather care, further research may investigate natural stabilizers or additives that can help natural formulations achieve similar performance in varying climates.

On the other hand, the natural shoe polish had a pH level comparable to commercial polish, making it safe for leather use. However, its slightly lower melting point suggests the need for adjustments on the ratio of the beeswax to increase the melting point. Future formulations may explore alternative waxes or slight modifications in its components, including the ratios to improve stability while maintaining its natural composition. Additionally, improvements in the

manufacturing process may enhance its consistency across formulations, ensuring that its stability.

Moreover, the glossiness on the natural shoe polish as assessed by the respondents' may be a viable alternative to conventional options that offer a comparable or even brighter shine. This supports the feasibility of producing shoe polish with coconut oil and beeswax, particularly for customers looking for natural substitutes without compromising quality. Likewise, further enhancements adding more components may improve its gloss.

Consequently, inferential analysis of pH level and melting point indicates that the natural shoe polish formulation meets the standards of commercially available products. This implies that beeswax and coconut oil can be utilized to make shoe polish effectively without harming its stability or usability. Nevertheless, further studies might evaluate its efficacy and long-term durability in different environmental settings.

Likewise, the shoe polish made from coconut oil (*C. nucifera*) and beeswax (*C. alba*) presents a sustainable and eco-friendly alternative with applications for both personal and commercial use. Its natural composition ensures the absence of harmful chemicals commonly found in synthetic polishes, making it a safer option for both individuals and the environment. Given these advantages, customers who value high-quality, environmentally sustainable leather care products will find this natural shoe polish ideal.

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Appendices

Appendix A

Collection of Raw Materials

Appendix B

Preparation of Raw Materials

Extraction of Oil from Coconut Waste

Melting of Beeswax

Appendix C

Preparation of the Natural Shoe Polish

Mixing of Coconut Oil and Beeswax

Appendix D

Material Testing and Measurements

Glossiness

pH Level

Melting Point

Appendix E

Sample Responses on Glossiness Questionnaire

Research Title: Coconut Oil (*Cocos nucifera*) and Beeswax (*Cera alba*) as a Natural Shoe Polish

DIRECTIONS: Please review the items below that describe the research being conducted for capstone. Kindly place a check mark in the appropriate box according to the scale provided.

6 Strongly agree 4 Slightly Agree 2 Disagree
 5 Agree 3 Slightly Disagree 1 Strongly Disagree

Gloss	Natural Shoe Polish						Commercialized Shoe Polish					
	6	5	4	3	2	1	6	5	4	3	2	1
1. The natural polish delivers a glossy finish upon application.	✓								✓			
2. The natural polish provides a lasting glossy finish on the leather.	✓							✓				
3. The natural shoe polish provides a long-lasting and consistent gloss over time.		✓						✓				
4. The natural shoe polish enhances the leather's natural gloss effectively.	✓								✓			
5. The polish does not leave streaks or uneven patches on the leather surface.	✓						✓					

1

Research Title: Coconut Oil (*Cocos nucifera*) and Beeswax (*Cera alba*) as a Natural Shoe Polish

DIRECTIONS: Please review the items below that describe the research being conducted for capstone. Kindly place a check mark in the appropriate box according to the scale provided.

6 Strongly agree 4 Slightly Agree 2 Disagree
 5 Agree 3 Slightly Disagree 1 Strongly Disagree

Gloss	Natural Shoe Polish						Commercialized Shoe Polish					
	6	5	4	3	2	1	6	5	4	3	2	1
1. The natural polish delivers a glossy finish upon application.	/							/				
2. The natural polish provides a lasting glossy finish on the leather.		/							/			
3. The natural shoe polish provides a long-lasting and consistent gloss over time.	/						/					
4. The natural shoe polish enhances the leather's natural gloss effectively.	/							/				
5. The polish does not leave streaks or uneven patches on the leather surface.	/						/					

2

Research Title: Coconut Oil (*Cocos nucifera*) and Beeswax (*Cera alba*) as a Natural Shoe Polish

DIRECTIONS: Please review the items below that describe the research being conducted for capstone. Kindly place a check mark in the appropriate box according to the scale provided.

- 6 Strongly agree 4 Slightly Agree 2 Disagree
 5 Agree 3 Slightly Disagree 1 Strongly Disagree

Gloss	Natural Shoe Polish						Commercialized Shoe Polish					
	6	5	4	3	2	1	6	5	4	3	2	1
1. The natural polish delivers a glossy finish upon application.		/					/					
2. The natural polish provides a lasting glossy finish on the leather.	/						/					
3. The natural shoe polish provides a long-lasting and consistent gloss over time.	/						/					
4. The natural shoe polish enhances the leather's natural gloss effectively.	/						/					
5. The polish does not leave streaks or uneven patches on the leather surface.	/						/					

DIRECTIONS: Please review the items below that describe the research being conducted for capstone. Kindly place a check mark in the appropriate box according to the scale provided.

- 6 Strongly agree 4 Slightly Agree 2 Disagree
 5 Agree 3 Slightly Disagree 1 Strongly Disagree

Gloss	Natural Shoe Polish						Commercialized Shoe Polish					
	6	5	4	3	2	1	6	5	4	3	2	1
1. The natural polish delivers a glossy finish upon application.	/						/					
2. The natural polish provides a lasting glossy finish on the leather.	/						/					
3. The natural shoe polish provides a long-lasting and consistent gloss over time.	/						/					
4. The natural shoe polish enhances the leather's natural gloss effectively.	/						/					
5. The polish does not leave streaks or uneven patches on the leather surface.	/						/					

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DIRECTIONS: Please review the items below that describe the research being conducted for capstone. Kindly place a check mark in the appropriate box according to the scale provided.

- 6 Strongly agree 4 Slightly Agree 2 Disagree 5
 5 Agree 3 Slightly Disagree 1 Strongly Disagree

Gloss	Natural Shoe Polish						Commercialized Shoe Polish					
	6	5	4	3	2	1	6	5	4	3	2	1
1. The natural polish delivers a glossy finish upon application.	/						/					
2. The natural polish provides a lasting glossy finish on the leather.	/						/					
3. The natural shoe polish provides a long-lasting and consistent gloss over time.	/						/					
4. The natural shoe polish enhances the leather's natural gloss effectively.	/						/					
5. The polish does not leave streaks or uneven patches on the leather surface.			/						/			

DIRECTIONS: Please review the items below that describe the research being conducted for capstone. Kindly place a check mark in the appropriate box according to the scale provided.

- 6 Strongly agree 4 Slightly Agree 2 Disagree 6
 5 Agree 3 Slightly Disagree 1 Strongly Disagree

Gloss	Natural Shoe Polish						Commercialized Shoe Polish					
	6	5	4	3	2	1	6	5	4	3	2	1
1. The natural polish delivers a glossy finish upon application.	/						/					
2. The natural polish provides a lasting glossy finish on the leather.	/						/					
3. The natural shoe polish provides a long-lasting and consistent gloss over time.	/						/					
4. The natural shoe polish enhances the leather's natural gloss effectively.	/						/					
5. The polish does not leave streaks or uneven patches on the leather surface.	/						/					

Appendix F

Tabulation and Data Analyses

Respondents' Assessment of Gloss

Respondent	Natural Shoe Polish					Commercial Shoe Polish				
	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5
1	6	6	5	6	6	4	5	5	4	6
2	6	5	6	6	6	5	4	6	5	5
3	5	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
4	6	6	6	6	6	5	6	4	6	6
5	6	6	6	6	4	6	6	5	4	4
6	6	6	6	6	6	5	5	5	5	5
7	6	6	6	6	5	4	3	5	5	2
8	6	5	5	5	6	6	5	5	4	4
9	6	6	6	6	6	5	5	5	5	6
10	5	5	6	6	5	5	5	6	6	5
11	6	6	6	6	6	3	1	1	3	3
12	6	6	5	6	6	6	6	5	6	6
13	6	6	5	6	6	6	6	5	6	5
14	6	6	5	6	6	5	6	6	6	6
15	6	6	5	6	6	5	6	5	6	4
16	6	6	5	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
17	6	6	6	6	6	4	4	3	2	2
18	6	6	6	6	6	6	4	4	6	4
19	6	6	6	6	6	5	6	5	6	6
20	6	6	5	4	5	6	4	4	5	3
21	5	5	4	5	5	3	3	2	5	5
22	6	5	6	6	6	5	4	5	5	5
23	6	6	6	6	5	5	4	4	4	4
24	6	5	6	5	5	6	6	6	6	6
25	6	5	5	6	6	5	5	5	5	6
26	6	6	6	6	6	5	4	4	5	5
27	6	6	6	6	6	4	4	3	4	4
28	6	6	6	6	6	5	4	4	5	5
29	6	6	6	6	5	5	5	6	6	3
30	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Answered	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
Not answered	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
Frequency										
Strongly Agree	27	23	20	26	22	10	11	8	13	11
Agree	3	7	9	3	7	14	7	12	10	8
Slightly Agree	0	0	1	1	1	4	9	6	5	6
Slightly Disagree	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	2	1	3
Disagree	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	2
Strongly Disagree	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
Total	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
Weighted Mean	Natural Shoe Polish					Commercial Shoe Polish				
	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5
	5.9	5.77	5.63	5.83	5.7	5.07	4.8	4.7	5.1	4.77
Overall Weighted Mean	5.77					4.89				

Appendix G

Inferential Data Analyses Using Rank Sum and Mann-Whitney U Test

Glossiness

GLOSSINESS				
Respondents	Glossiness Average		Rank	
	NSP	CSP	NSP	CSP
1	5.8	4.8	38.50	12.00
2	5.8	5.0	38.50	16.50
3	5.8	6.0	38.50	53.00
4	6.0	5.4	53.00	25.00
5	5.6	5.0	29.50	16.50
6	6.0	5.0	53.00	16.50
7	5.8	3.8	38.50	4.50
8	5.4	4.8	25.00	12.00
9	6.0	5.2	53.00	20.50
10	5.4	5.4	25.00	25.00
11	6.0	2.2	53.00	1.00
12	5.8	5.8	38.50	38.50
13	5.8	5.6	38.50	29.50
14	5.8	5.8	38.50	38.50
15	5.8	5.2	38.50	20.50
16	5.8	6.0	38.50	53.00
17	6.0	3.0	53.00	2.00
18	6.0	4.8	53.00	12.00
19	6.0	5.6	53.00	29.50
20	5.2	4.4	20.50	7.00
21	4.8	3.6	12.00	3.00
22	5.8	4.8	38.50	12.00
23	5.8	4.2	38.50	6.00
24	5.4	6.0	25.00	53.00
25	5.6	5.2	29.50	20.50
26	6.0	4.6	53.00	8.50
27	6.0	3.8	53.00	4.50
28	6.0	4.6	53.00	8.50
29	5.8	5.0	38.50	16.50
30	6.0	6.0	53.00	53.00
		Rank Sum	1211.50	618.50
		Sample Size	30	30
Test 1			Test 2	
U1	746.5		Mann-Whitney Test for Two Independent Samples	
U2	153.5		NSP	CSP
U	153.5		count	30
CV	317		median	5.0
Critical value of U = 317			rank sum	1211.5
U=153.5 < CV = 317			U	153.5
Decision: Reject the Ho				746.5
			one tail	two tail
			U	153.5
			mean	450
			std dev	67.63874629
			z-score	4.376189924
			effect r	0.56496369
			p-norm	0.0000604
				0.00001208
			Reject the Ho	
			There is significant difference	

pH Level

Melting Point

pH level				
Trial	NSP	CSP	Rank	
			NSP	CSP
I	6.56	6.7	2	5.5
II	6.86	6.66	9	4
III	6.7	6.65	5.5	3
IV	6.8	6.75	8	7
V	6.89	6.46	10	1
Rank Sum			34.50	20.50
Sample Size			5	5
Test 1				
U1	19.5			
U2	5.5	Critical value of U = 2		
U	5.5	U=5.5 > CV = 2		
CV	2	Decision: Fail to reject		
Test 2				
Mann-Whitney Test for Two Independent Samples				
	NSP	CSP		
count	5	5		
median	6.8	6.66		
rank sum	34.5	20.5		
U	5.5	19.5		
	one tail	two tail		
U	5.5			
mean	12.5			
std dev	4.787136			
z-score	1.357806			
effect r	0.429376			
p-norm	0.087263	0.174525	Fail to reject Ho	
No significant difference				

Melting Point				
Trial	NSP	CSP	Rank	
			NSP	CSP
I	58	58.5	3	4
II	57	61	2	10
III	54	60.5	1	9
IV	59.5	60	6.5	8
V	59.5	59	6.5	5
Rank Sum			19.00	36.00
Sample Size			5	5
Test 1				
U1	4			
U2	21	Critical value of U = 2		
U	4	U=4 > CV = 2		
CV	2	Decision: Fail to reject		
Test 2				
Mann-Whitney Test for Two Independent Samples				
	NSP	CSP		
count	5	5		
median	58	60		
rank sum	19	36		
U	21	4		
	one tail	two tail		
U	4			
mean	12.5			
std dev	4.7871355			
z-score	1.6711455			
effect r	0.5284626			
p-norm	0.0473465	0.0946929	Fail to reject Ho	
No significant difference				

Appendix F
Cost Analysis

MATERIALS	AMOUNT	CONSUMPTION	PRICE
Beeswax	₱45 per 100 grams	100 grams	₱45
Desiccated/ Shredded coconut waste	₱0	5 kilograms	₱0
Denatured Alcohol	₱40	1 bottle	₱40
Total Price			₱85